

**METHODOLOGICAL BASES FOR IMPROVING ENGLISH TEACHING THROUGH
EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT WORK OF HEIs STUDENTS (ON
THE EXAMPLE OF INDIVIDUALIZATION AND DIFFERENTIATION)**

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***Abstract.** This article reveals the problem of using various forms of independent work in educational and cognitive activities, which contributes to the formation of a comprehensively developed personality of a student who is ready for creative activity. It should be noted that the strategies of student-centered and differentiated pedagogy, and approaches to teaching a modern student are closely related to the proper organization of independent work in the conditions of university training and should reflect the characteristics of the natural development of a young person, as well as the professional orientation of the individual.*

***Keywords :** educational objectives, orientation of education, strategies, professional orientation, pedagogical conditions, potential opportunities, optimal path.*

INTRODUCTION The current pace of development of technology and society as a whole reflects new demands on the goals and objectives of education, forms and methods of teaching, in other words, directly on the pedagogical process. Priority among the mandatory requirements is the focus of the educational system on the formation of the personality of the individual, taking into account and developing various abilities, interests and talents [2,7]. It should be noted that the strategies of student-centered and differentiated pedagogy, and approaches to teaching a modern student are closely related to the proper organization of independent work in the conditions of university training and should reflect the characteristics of the natural development of a young person (personality orientation, intelligence level, general and special abilities, gender and age). features, character, temperament and more), the level of development of modern science, technology and culture, the psychologization of the processes of education and training, as well as the professional orientation of the individual . in other words, personalism and anthropologism based on worldviews are developed and concretized to the level of private methods. Determining the importance of independent work in the educational process of the university and the professional training of students, it is necessary to identify under what pedagogical conditions the improvement of students' independent work using Internet resources will be effective. The use of various forms of independent work in educational and cognitive activities contributes to the formation of a comprehensively developed personality of a student who is ready for creative activity. Therefore, the problem arises of finding general and particular methodological foundations for all components of the design process of teachers and personal design of students' independent work. The concept of humanization of higher education allows us to take a fresh look at the potential for independent work of students and their productive use for individual personal development and self-development of students at the value-motivational, informational, activity and communicative levels. The center of modern pedagogical science and practice is increasingly becoming the personality of a person, his qualities, needs and interests, the dominant motives of activity and behavior, which urgently requires all those working with a personality to recognize its uniqueness, intellectual and moral freedom, and the right to respect.

This becomes possible if the basic value orientation is a setting for dialogue interaction, which involves providing assistance and pedagogical support to a person in realizing himself as a person, identifying and revealing his capabilities, implementing socially acceptable self-realization and self-affirmation that are personally significant to him.

METHODOLOGY In the process of mastering the training program for mid-level specialists, most of the study time is devoted to independent work of students. Independent work of students is a part of the training, carried out on the instructions and with the methodological guidance of the teacher, but without his direct participation. For better assimilation of the material, students need to engage in independent work. The role of the teacher is to organize independent work with the aim of acquiring general and professional competencies by the student, allowing the student to develop the ability for self-development, self-education and innovation. The role of the student is to become a creative person in the process of independent work under the guidance of a teacher, able to independently acquire knowledge, skills and possessions, formulate a problem and find the best way to solve it.

Pedagogical design in student-centered (individualized) learning can be carried out in two stages:

1. Preliminary design as subject-object in nature of relations;
2. Individual as a subject-subject by the nature of the relationship.

The essence of many pedagogical studies of a personality-oriented approach is as follows: until personal values, meanings, relationships are taken into account, pedagogical technologies will not work. When developing a strategy for the development of the educational space, one should focus on the manifestation of the individuality of the participants in the pedagogical process, for which: "... include the activities of teachers and students in the project so that innovation has personal meaning for them; when developing the content of actions, focus on the individual originality of the implementation of these actions by specific participants in the educational process; provide for the formation in the educational process of conditions that allow the qualities of individuality to be realized; include in the innovation criteria indicators that reveal the content and implementation of the individuality of the participants in the pedagogical process, for example, independent creative proposals, author's programs, manifestation of creative nature" [6,9].

When planning independent work, goals should be defined, in particular:

- consolidation, deepening, expansion and systematization of knowledge and skills acquired during classroom lessons;
- independent mastery of educational material;
- formation of skills of search and use of reference and special literature;
- development of cognitive abilities and activity, creative initiative, independence, responsibility and organization;
- development of research skills [2,7] The formation of the skill of independent learning activities goes through several stages in its development and begins with short-term tasks performed during the training session.

A differentiated approach to independent work includes the following components:

- increase in the volume of intensive work with more prepared students;
- division of classes into compulsory and creative parts; regularity of consultations with the trainee;

- comprehensive and timely information about the thematic content of independent work, deadlines, the need for auxiliary tools, forms, methods of monitoring and evaluating the final results [2,11].

The differentiation of students' independent work tasks depends on the time of study. At the beginning of the study of the discipline, independent work aims to expand and consolidate the knowledge and skills gained in lectures and practical exercises, in the future it contributes to the development of creative potential and the implementation of professional knowledge. Tasks in this case can be both individual and group in nature, since real professional conditions in most cases are based on work in a team: presentation, business game, analysis of a specific educational situation, group project. In the educational process, two types of independent work are used: classroom and extracurricular. Classroom independent work is carried out under the direct supervision of the teacher and on his instructions.

RESULTS The productivity of such work largely depends on methodological techniques that promote the activation of mental activity. This approach allows you to change the relationship between the teacher and the student, creating the basis for a learning dialogue. In connection with the natural transition from the informing to the formative system of education, the functions of the teacher also change: the priority now is not the informational, but the consultative coordinating function, which once again emphasizes the significant place of independent work in teaching students. In order to correctly determine the choice of a task for independent work, its compliance with the place of performance, the composition of students, and the level of abilities, one should use the system of individual tasks proposed by I.E.Unt, which provides for the following groups of tasks:

I. Types of individual tasks. 1. Mandatory tasks proposed by the teacher. 2. Alternative tasks proposed by the teacher (i.e. selective, when the student must choose himself). 3. Tasks proposed by the teacher for voluntary implementation. 4. Voluntary tasks, the content of which is found by the student himself.

II. Tasks on the composition of students. 1. General (for the whole group). 2. Microgroup tasks (one task for a microgroup). 3. Differentiated tasks (by microgroups , but with different content, types of students' independent work). 4. Individualized or student-centered tasks.

III. Tasks by ability level. 1. Tasks that take into account the level of students (tasks for taking into account preliminary knowledge; tasks aimed at eliminating gaps in knowledge). 2. Tasks that take into account general and individual abilities (the pace of learning, performance, fatigue). 3. Tasks that take into account the cognitive interest of students.

DISCUSSION An important role in this direction can be played by the organization of students' independent work. A characteristic feature of students' independent work as a specific type of learning activity is the presence of a dual goal: the formation of independence as a personality trait and the assimilation of theoretical knowledge in conjunction with the formation of practical skills [6,14]. We note the most common signs of student independence both in teaching English and in teaching other subjects: the desire and ability to immediately engage in independent activities; the desire to solve the problem in different ways; introduction of elements of rationalization in the performance of practical and laboratory work; the ability to critically approach facts; the ability to transfer knowledge and skills to a new situation. The implementation of a differentiated approach to the organization of independent work seems to be

the most effective, since it is aimed at the most complete and successful implementation by each individual student of his abilities and capabilities in learning English.

CONCLUSIONS Realizing that the result of its implementation depends on the clear planning of independent work of students, plans should be developed, schedules, guidance for independent work of students and teachers. In addition, for each lesson, a comprehensive plan should be drawn up to guide students' independent work, taking into account their level of professional knowledge. The multi-level organization of independent work of students on the basis of professional knowledge, skills, serves as a motivation for professional activity in the process of lectures, practical classes and extracurricular activities. work, which in turn contributes to a significant increase in the professionalism of future secondary school teachers.

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